

Cosmic dissonance: new physics or systematics behind the Hubble tension?

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The Hubble tension

The Hubble constant (H_0) is a fundamental cosmological parameter that determines the expansion rate of the Universe in the past, present and future. Additionally, it is an essential quantity for calibrating the cosmic distance scale and calculating the age of the Universe. Despite its importance in cosmology, its value is a matter of strong debate. Local determinations of the Hubble constant using Cepheids and type Ia supernovae find $H_0 = 73.2 \pm 1.3 \text{ km s}^{-1} \text{ Mpc}^{-1}$ [1], while observations from the cosmic microwave background (CMB) radiation obtain $H_0 = 67.4 \pm 0.5 \text{ km s}^{-1} \text{ Mpc}^{-1}$ [2]. This difference is one of the most outstanding problems in present-day cosmology and is often referred to as the *Hubble tension*. The discrepancy might be explained by some residual systematics in any of the measurements, but it also questions our understanding of the Universe. Since the CMB-based method needs a cosmological model to extrapolate the parameters measured at recombination to redshift zero, it uses the standard Λ CDM model. In other words, if the true underlying cosmology deviates from Λ CDM, this might explain why the CMB measures a different H_0 than local measurements.

The main question that I will answer in this proceeding is the following: *Can modifications of Λ CDM solve the Hubble tension?* The results and conclusions presented here are from [3].

The importance of the sound horizon

Contrary to what the name might suggest, the Hubble tension is about more than just H_0 . Another important cosmological parameter that we focus on in our work is the sound horizon (r_d). The sound horizon characterizes a distance scale in the early Universe, when the baryons and photons were trapped in a primordial plasma. Any over-densities in the plasma would lead to gravitational collapse, as well as a radiation pressure directed outwards. The counteracting forces of gravity and pressure resulted in oscillations, very similar to sound waves. The sound horizon constitutes the maximum distance the sound waves have travelled before the Universe became transparent at the epoch of recombination.

Today, we can still observe this characteristic scale in the distribution of galaxies and clusters, as more structures have formed at a separation of r_d . Baryon Acoustic Oscillation (BAO) measurements use the clustering of galaxies to extract this feature. By comparing the radius of the sound horizon at recombination to the sound horizon at lower red-shifts, the product of $H_0 \times r_d$ can be constrained. Therefore, the Hubble tension is just as much a tension in the sound horizon. Measurements of the CMB find a low H_0 and a high r_d , while several local measurements obtain a high H_0 and a low r_d .

Data sets

In our work, we employ observations of type Ia supernovae (SNe) and BAO as relative distance measurements. These probes can be calibrated by absolute distance measurements of Cepheid variable stars, as carried out by the *Supernovae and H_0 for the Equation of State of dark energy* project (SH0ES; [1]), or from stars at the Tip of the Red Giant Branch (TRGB), obtained by the Carnegie-Chicago Hubble Program (CCHP; [4]). However, Cepheids and TRGB stars can only be observed at low red-shifts. For that reason, we are using an additional calibration from gravitationally lensed quasars, as measured by the *H_0 Lenses in COSMOGRAIL's Wellspring* collaboration (H0LiCOW; [5]). By measuring the time-delays between brightness fluctuations of the multiple images of the quasar, absolute distances between the observer, lens galaxy and the quasar can be determined. The advantage of lensed quasars is that they allow for a calibration at higher red-shifts.

Tension between CMB and local observations

Our measurements of the sound horizon are summarized below, together with the CMB constraints by *Planck* for a comparison.

SNe + BAO + H0LiCOW:	$r_d = 134.2 \pm 4.4 \text{ Mpc}$
SNe + BAO + H0LiCOW + SH0ES:	$r_d = 135.1 \pm 2.9 \text{ Mpc}$
SNe + BAO + H0LiCOW + CCHP:	$r_d = 139.5 \pm 3.6 \text{ Mpc}$
CMB (<i>Planck</i>):	$r_d = 147.2 \pm 0.3 \text{ Mpc}$

When type Ia supernovae and BAO are calibrated by a combination of Cepheid measurements by SH0ES and lensed quasars from H0LiCOW, our combined $H_0 - r_d$ results are in 5σ tension with observations from the CMB.

Figure 1: Expansion history of the Universe as predicted by the Λ CDM model (black), early-time modifications (red) and late-time modifications (blue).

However, the tension is lowered considerably if we replace the SH0ES calibration by that of the TRGB by the CCHP collaboration.

Local measurements can be obtained without assumptions about the underlying cosmological model, whereas the CMB analysis require one; hence, they use Λ CDM. This raises the question whether modifications to Λ CDM might be able to shift the CMB results closer to the local ones and reconcile the tension.

Modifications of Λ CDM

Extensions to the standard cosmological model can follow two distinct approaches; they can either change the early-time physics (pre-recombination) or they can change the late-time physics (post-recombination).

Early-time modifications introduce an additional component in the early Universe, such as additional relativistic particles ('dark radiation') or early dark energy, which increases the expansion rate. This reduces the time between the Big Bang and recombination and, in turn, decreases the maximum distance the sound waves could travel before recombination. As such, the radius of the sound horizon is shorter than in the standard Λ CDM scenario. Since we still observe the same angular size of the sound horizon in the CMB power spectrum, this automatically implies a shorter angular diameter distance to the CMB. Shorter distances corresponds to a higher Hubble constant. In this way, early-time modifications alter simultaneously the Hubble constant and the sound horizon.

Late-time modifications, on the other hand, leave the physics before recombination unaltered. Instead, they impose a phase of extra accelerated expansion at later times. This is generally achieved by modifying the dark energy density such that it increases over time, which eventually leads to the 'Big Rip' scenario in which cosmic expansion will rip everything in the Universe apart. On the bright side, this scenario has the potential to solve the Hubble tension by increasing the present-day expansion rate. However, as the physics of the early Universe is unchanged, these models cannot alter the value of the sound horizon.

Figure 1 illustrates how early-time and late-time models change the expansion history of the Universe.

Results

In order to study the effects that modifications of Λ CDM have on the tension, we investigated four models that are commonly used in the literature. Figure 2 shows how the $H_0 - r_d$ contours from the CMB change after applying these models. The early-time models (dark radiation and early dark energy) move both H_0 and r_d closer to their local values. Although, in the case of local data calibrated by SH0ES and H0LiCOW measurements, the shift is not sufficient to solve the tension. Late-time extensions (dark

energy models 1 and 2) increase H_0 but are not able to alter the value of r_d ; they fail to address the combined tension.

Additionally, it has recently been pointed out that both early-time and late-time modifications exacerbate the mild growth tension that exists between CMB and large scale structure measurements.

Conclusions

Returning to the original question; *can modifications of Λ CDM solve the Hubble tension?*

In my opinion, the answer is no. Early-time modifications slightly reduce the tension, but create a new problem when it comes to the growth tension, while late-time modifications fail to address the combined tension completely, since they cannot alter the value of the sound horizon.

Figure 2: The effects of modifications of Λ CDM (coloured contours) on the CMB observations from *Planck* (black contours). The filled gray contours correspond to the 2σ credibility regions of local observations (SNe + BAO + H0LiCOW + SH0ES/CCHP). Early-time models (dark radiation and early dark energy) shift both H_0 and r_d closer to the local values, while late-time models (dark energy models 1 and 2) only change the Hubble constant and, therefore, fail to solve the combined tension. Figure adapted from [3].

References

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